

APPROACHES TO TEACHING ACADEMIC WRITING

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ABSTRACT: The article describes the difficulties that students face when mastering a written language in a foreign language course in English for Academic Purposes in the context of the specifics of the course. Methodological approaches to teaching foreign language written speech are analyzed, their strengths and weaknesses are identified, the possibility of using tasks inherent in these approaches in the course of academic writing to overcome the described difficulties is considered. Examples are given illustrating how tasks can be combined when writing an essay and annotation.

KEYWORDS: approach, discuss, critically evaluate, compare and contrast.

Students whose first language is not English often have significant difficulties with some aspects of English grammar that are distinct from the problems that native English speakers have. These include: choice of article, a, an or the; word order; prepositions, on, at, in, etc. Often universities provide English language support for them and you may be able to arrange 'team teaching' if you have large numbers of international students. Team teaching is when language specialists, for example, record lectures and then work with the subject specialist to design materials to support students in their learning of both the language and the content. It is beyond the scope of this book to examine the writing problems of international students in detail. In dealing with text types, rhetorical purpose, register and grammatical accuracy we have focused on features of the final written text. We turn now to ways of helping students with the process of producing that writing. Exactly how individual tutors support students' writing varies across, and indeed within, the range of institutional provision outlined in the previous section. However, there are three influential approaches to the teaching of student writing that it is useful to consider. We refer to these approaches in the following way: writing as text, writing as process and writing as social practice. Such approaches have developed over time and often in distinct geographical contexts but to a greater or lesser extent they inform how writing is currently being taught. Historically, when writing has been explicitly taught in higher education, the emphasis has been on students' writing as final texts or 'products'. Teaching writing -

whether in formal writing classes or as an activity within discipline-based courses – often entailed presenting students with ‘models of good writing’, and asking them to imitate these exemplars. Often, little analysis occurred of the various rhetorical aspects of the texts or the social contexts in which the texts functioned. We look at some specific features of academic text including text types, rhetorical purpose, register and linguistic accuracy. While many of these features may seem obvious, often students, especially those just entering tertiary education, find it far from straightforward to know exactly what is expected. Words such as ‘essay’, ‘laboratory report’ and ‘case study’ are problematic in that they denote a wide variety of types of text. For ease of reference in discussing text types we continue to use these labels, but we emphasize that you cannot assume that the knowledge of what to expect in a certain text type is shared by students. The essay, for example, may contain different elements depending on whether it is framed as a critical review, a discussion, a personal response or an exposition. Our implicit knowledge of what to expect from text types in response to certain prompts, such as ‘discuss’, ‘critically evaluate’, ‘compare and contrast’, informs the judgements that we make about the success of students’ texts as a whole. The way we can generalize text types enables us as teachers to isolate certain traits and make them explicit to students, but we need to bear in mind that text types vary in response to the function that a text performs, which is not always reflected in the descriptive term applied to it.

An important point about a scaffolding approach to teaching and learning writing is that whilst guidance and help are essential, the ultimate aim is to achieve what is sometimes referred to as ‘handover’; that is the point at which the ‘expert’ tutor or lecturer hands over responsibility to the student for their own writing. Students often feel they must try to ‘give tutors what they want’ and to ‘play it safe’ and may go through the whole of their university studies without feeling that they should take responsibility for the writing that they do. Given the higher education aim of developing autonomy and critical awareness, students need to be encouraged to see that they can make choices about how they write in academia. It may be useful to discuss with students the kinds of issues they face in making choices and taking responsibility for their own writing.

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